

BRIDGING EMPLOYABILITY GAP IN TECHNICAL EDUCATION: LANGUAGE AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS AS PANACEA IN HYBRID WORK ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract

The Covid 19 pandemic abruptly affected traditional way of life in many counties leading to people working remotely in order to prevent its further spread. This adversely affected many economies as companies began to incorporate a mixture of in-office and remote schedules in their activities. Countries not digitally ready were mainly affected, Nigeria inclusive. It is worrisome that the number of graduates churned out by the polytechnics in Nigeria continues to outpace the availability of employment opportunities in the hybrid environment. Against this backdrop, the present study empirically examined the extent to which language and communication skills predict future-ready competencies among HND2 polytechnic students who are due for the labour market. Using a descriptive survey research design, the study involved 200 final-year students from Federal Polytechnic, Nekede and State Polytechnic, Omuma as well as 15 GNS lecturers and 8 industry employers in Imo State. Six research questions guided the Study. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire. The data were analysed using both descriptive statistics and inferential methods, including correlation and regression analyses. The findings showed that students demonstrated inadequate competencies for a hybrid work environment. The study provided empirical support to address the employability gap in technical and vocational education.

Key words: Communication Skills, Technical Education. Employability Gap, Hybrid

Introduction

In contemporary labour markets, employability is no longer defined solely by technical expertise but increasingly by the possession of transferable “soft” skills, particularly in communication competence. The existence of the world as a global village further makes it easier for people to work remotely. The rapid transformation of work environments driven by digitization, automation, and Industry 4.0 has further intensified the need for effective communication skills. This accounts for the new trend with employers emphatic on graduates’ ability to articulate ideas clearly, collaborate effectively, and adapt their language to diverse professional and digital contexts (Yorke, 2006; Robles, 2012). In line with the above, modern offices anticipate technical professionals who are expected to produce technical reports, interpret manuals, deliver presentations, collaborate in virtual teams, and engage in multimodal communication that integrates text, visuals, and digital platforms (OECD, 2019).

Technical education institutions originally established to produce middle position skilled manpower are under increasing pressure to graduate individuals who are not only technically proficient but also effective communicators. This calls for a shift from traditional technical curricula limited relevance to real work demands (Male, Bush, & Chapman, 2011), to prioritized hands-on and practical competencies.

While higher education institutions traditionally focus on subject-specific knowledge, today's employers increasingly prioritize graduates who demonstrate strong communication skills, critical thinking and problem-solving abilities which will enable them to fit into the few existing spaces. This has led to emerging questions as to whether higher education providers are giving students the right opportunities to foster their professional skills and provide a seamless transition into the workforce. These expectations are yet to be met as there is a persistent employability gap in graduates' communication skills, particularly among products of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) institutions (UNESCO, 2015; World Economic Forum, 2020

Growing concerns about graduates' communication competence remain a recurring issue among employers of daily operations (Redecker, 2017). Due to the inability to effectively communicate in the workplace, many graduates with desirable technical abilities continue to be unemployed or underemployed. These deficiencies are often exhibited through writing, limited vocabulary in the workplace, poor speech expressions, and lack of confidence in professional contacts. Some of these deficiencies have been linked to teacher-centered teaching methods, out-of-date curricula, poor integration of language education with technical material, and insufficient contact hours for communication courses (Ayonmike, Okwelle, & Okeke, 2015). Language and communication courses are viewed as incidental or entirely theoretical needs in polytechnic education, especially in technology-oriented programs where instructional emphasis is mostly on technical ability. To this effect, students' preparedness for technology-mediated workplaces, where emails, virtual meetings, collaborative platforms, and visual communication are essential components of everyday operations, is undermined by the scant incorporation of digital tools in communication skills instruction (Redecker, 2017).

In view of the above problems, a systematic and intentional approach is needed to close the employability gap in communication skills within technical education. Adopting learner-centered and technology-enhanced pedagogies, aligning curricula with industry communication needs, contextualizing communication instruction within particular technical disciplines, and enhancing industry-educational collaboration are all components of this approach (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018). A comprehensive grasp of a clear understanding of the nature, causes, and implications of communication skill deficiencies is therefore essential for designing sustainable interventions that enhance graduate employability. In light of this, the current study examines methods for closing the employability gap and looks into communication skills deficiencies among technical education students. The study aims to produce empirical evidence that can guide curriculum reform, pedagogical innovation, and policy initiatives targeted at generating graduates who are both technically adept and communicatively competent by concentrating on the development of communication skills within technical education.

Statement of the Problem

The poor level of digital literacy in polytechnic education coupled with the ever watering-down of the National Board for Technical Education, (NBTE) curriculum have engendered the graduation of half baked-students incapable of filling the employment spaces in the digital era, especially, in a hybrid work environment. Few empirical studies explicitly look at how language and communication abilities affect future-ready competencies, among polytechnic students. This study fills a gap in knowledge by addressing how language and communication skills can help polytechnic students to develop future-ready competencies in order to bridge the digital divide and close the employment gap.

Objectives of the Study

The study seeks to:

- i. Examine the level of communication skills possessed by students in technical education institutions;
- ii. Identify the communication skills required by employers for effective performance in technical and vocational workplaces;
- iii. Determine the extent to which existing technical education curricula address employability-oriented communication skills;
- iv. Investigate the teaching and learning approaches used in developing communication skills in technical education programmes;
- v. Examine the challenges affecting the effective acquisition of communication skills among technical education students; and
- vi. Propose pedagogical and curricular strategies for bridging the employability gap in communication skills within technical education.

Research Questions:

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the level of communication skills among HND 2 students in technical education institutions?
- ii. Which communication skills do employers consider essential for employability in technical and vocational occupations?
- iii. To what extent do current technical education curricula incorporate employability-focused communication skills?
- iv. What teaching and learning approaches are used to develop students' communication skills in technical education programmes?
- v. What challenges hinder the effective development of communication skills among technical education students?
- vi. What strategies can be adopted to bridge the employability gap in communication skills in technical education?

Conceptual Review:

Communication Skills: The ability to effectively utilize communication skills involve the effective transmission and interpretation of information through oral, written, non-verbal, and digital modes. In technical and vocational contexts, these skills include technical writing, report preparation, workplace presentations, interpretation of manuals and diagrams, interpersonal interaction, and the use of digital tools such as emails, collaborative platforms, and virtual meeting

technologies (Robles, 2012). One's ability to effectively communicate entails his/her ability to explain complex ideas, participate in teamwork, adhere to safety and operational standards, and interact productively with supervisors, colleagues, and clients. These skills are in high demand in remote and hybrid work environments. To this end, acquisition of these tools have become inevitable in the world of work as virtual meetings, online collaboration tools, and digital communication platforms have become integral to daily work life. While these tools offer flexibility and efficiency, they also demand a new set of communication norms and soft skills expected of the modern day graduate.

Technical Education: Technical education comprises education and training programmes aimed at equipping learners with applied knowledge, practical skills, and competencies required for specific occupations, trades, and professions. Polytechnics and technical colleges play a vital role in producing middle-level manpower for national development. However, the strong emphasis on practical skills acquisition often results in limited attention to communication and language development, despite their importance for workplace effectiveness (Billett, 2011). This imbalance significantly contributes to the employability gap experienced by many technical education graduates.

Employability Gap in Communication Skills: Employability refers to a graduate's ability to obtain an employment, sustain same and even be able to secure new employment when necessary. It encompasses not only technical knowledge and disciplinary competence but also a broad range of transferable skills, attitudes, and attributes valued by employers (Yorke, 2006). Employability skills are essentially the collection of qualities that allow people not only to find jobs but also succeed in it and positively impact their workplaces (Olabimitan & Akindele 2023). In technical education, employability increasingly involves the effective application of technical knowledge, clear communication, collaborative work practices, and adaptability to changing workplace demands as observed in hybrid situations. International skills frameworks developed by organisations such as UNESCO and the World Economic Forum consistently identify communication skills as a core component of employability in the 21st-century workforce.

The employability gap in communication skills refers to the mismatch between the communication competencies graduates possess and those demanded by employers. While graduates may demonstrate adequate technical proficiency, deficiencies in oral communication, professional writing, teamwork interaction, and digital literacy frequently limit their workplace effectiveness (Male, Bush, & Chapman, 2011). The emergence of Industry 4.0 and digitally driven workplaces has further widened this gap, as employers increasingly seek graduates with multimodal communication skills that integrate text, visuals, and technology (OECD, 2019). Bridging the employability gap therefore requires the intentional integration of communication training into technical curricula.

Hybrid Environments: Advancement in technology has brought about changes in all spheres of human endeavour, the work environment inclusive. Just like teaching is advocating the incorporation of modern technologies to advance skills, work places are also seeking employees who are able to adapt to the expectations of a hybrid environments. A hybrid job enables a kind of flexibility that blends, allowing the individual the ability to switch and combine both the traditional and the modern skills required in the working environment (Gilstrap et al., 2022).

Hybrid work is distinct from virtual work in that it provides the areas of collaboration for team members and enables individuals to be at their best in the necessary needed skills.

Theoretical Review: The main theories that are pertinent to this research are Human Capital Theory, Mismatch theory and Constructivist Learning Theory

Human Capital Theory: This theory helps to explain certain issues of employability in technical education. Schultz (1961) created the idea, and Becker (1964) improved it. It highlights how investing in education, training, and skill development boosts people's output and marketability. The idea being that education gives people the knowledge, abilities, and skills needed for work and economic productivity in anticipation of benefits like increased income, better employment prospects, and career progression. Human Capital Theory encourages the creation of curricula in technical education that prioritize skills that are applicable to the workplace. Graduates from technical schools are more employable and productive when they receive training relevant to the industry. However, when training does not match the demands of the labor market, employability disparities may persist despite investments in education.

Skills Mismatch Theory: Skills Mismatch Theory explains the gap between the skills possessed by graduates and those required by employers in the labour market. The theory suggests that unemployment and underemployment occur when individuals' qualifications, competencies, and abilities do not correspond with job requirements (McGuinness, 2006). Technological changes, outdated curricula, and inadequate industry collaboration in educational systems can account for the mismatch. The resultant effect is that many employers report that graduates lack practical skills, communication abilities, problem-solving competencies, and digital literacy required in modern workplaces (Jim Allen & Rolf van der Velden, 2011). As new technologies continue to evolve, educational institutions that fail to integrate emerging technologies into their curriculum will continue to contribute to the widening employability gaps (World Bank, 2019). The need therefore arises for collaborations in order for institutional output to match the industries' expectation.

Constructivist Learning Theory: According to Piaget's Constructivist Learning Theory (1972), students build knowledge by actively participating and engaging in practical activities. Competency-based education, which is crucial in technical education, is supported by this philosophy. Conversely, Vygotsky's (1978) Social Constructivism promotes active learning, problem-solving, and skill development through practical experiences. This method improves the technical proficiency, creativity, and critical thinking required for employability. Constructivist technical education institutes emphasize skill mastery, collaborative learning, and project-based learning. These tactics aid in closing the employment gap. They boost creativity and innovation in polytechnic education by supporting and encouraging project-based learning theory.

Empirical Studies

International studies consistently highlight communication skills deficits among technical and engineering graduates. Male, Bush, & Chapman (2011) found that Australian employers ranked communication skills above many technical competencies, yet graduates demonstrated low proficiency in professional writing and oral presentations. Similarly, an OECD (2019) report revealed that although technical graduates often possess job-specific skills, many lack the

communication and collaboration abilities required in digital and team-based workplaces. Billett (2011) further reported that technical and vocational students exposed to authentic workplace communication tasks during training achieved better employability outcomes than those taught using traditional lecture-based methods, underscoring the value of experiential and contextualised learning.

In developing countries, the employability gap in communication skills is often more pronounced due to structural and pedagogical constraints. UNESCO (2015) observed that TVET institutions in many developing economies prioritize technical skill acquisition at the expense of transferable skills, resulting in graduates who are technically trained but inadequately prepared for workplace communication. Employer dissatisfaction with graduates' oral and written communication skills has been widely reported across Asia and Africa (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018).

In Nigeria, empirical evidence reveals significant communication skills deficits among technical education graduates. Okolie, Nwajiuba, and Binuomote (2019) reported that employers rated graduates low in oral communication, report writing, and professional interaction despite adequate technical competence. Additional studies indicate that communication courses in Nigerian polytechnics are often generic and disconnected from students' technical disciplines, limiting their workplace relevance (Eze & Igbokwe, 2018). Furthermore, research shows that teacher-centred pedagogies reduce opportunities for students to practice communication skills through presentations, group work, and problem-solving activities (Okoro & Washington, 2012). Ayonmike, Okwelle, and Okeke (2015) identified outdated curricula, insufficient instructional time for communication courses, and weak industry collaboration as major contributors to this employability gap. An instance, in the currently reviewed NBTE (2025) curriculum for HND 1I, with glaring absence of the multimodal skills required in the hybrid work environment of the 21st century. Overall, empirical evidence consistently demonstrates that communication skills are critical determinants of employability, yet, they remain inadequately developed within technical education.

Methodology

Research Design

In order to experimentally investigate the degree to which language and communication skills predict future-ready competences among polytechnic students, this study used a descriptive survey research approach. The methodical gathering of data from a wide range of respondents was made possible by the descriptive survey methodology, which allowed for the description and explanation of the variables being studied.

Population and Sample

The target population comprised final-year students, General Studies (GNS) lecturers, and industry employers in Imo State, Nigeria. A total of 223 participants were involved in the study, consisting of 200 final-year students drawn from Federal Polytechnic, Nekede and State Polytechnic, Omuma, alongside 15 GNS lecturers and 8 industry employers. The final-year students constituted the largest respondent group (89.7%), given that they were considered the most proximate to entering the hybrid work environment. The gender composition of the sample was 117 males (52.5%) and 106 females (47.5%).

Research Instrument

A systematic questionnaire with six sections was used to gather data. Demographic data was collected in Section A. With items assessed on a 5-point Likert-type scale, Sections B through F addressed the study's six research issues. Section C asked employers to rank the communication abilities necessary for employment; Section B evaluated students' self-rated communication competence (1 = Very Low to 5 = Very High); Section F assessed the degree of obstacles impeding the development of effective communication skills; Section E looked at the frequency of teaching and learning methodologies utilized in communication skills training; and Section D assessed respondents' judgments of curriculum adequacy. The dependability of the questionnaire was determined before it was administered, and it was verified by subject-matter experts.

Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used to analyze the data. To ascertain the amount and distribution of replies, descriptive statistics, namely the mean (M) and standard deviation (SD), were calculated for each item and section. For the purpose of understanding mean scores across parts, a scale midpoint of 3.0 was used. Three layers of inferential analysis were carried out. To ascertain whether observed patterns were statistically significant, one-sample t-tests were first performed to the composite scores of each section to ascertain whether mean responses deviated substantially from the scale midpoint (3.0). Second, the bivariate correlations between the main study variables—student communication skills, employer requirements, curriculum adequacy, teaching strategies, and perceived challenges—were examined using Pearson product-moment correlation analysis. Third, multiple regression analysis was performed with student communication skills (Section B composite) as the dependent variable and curriculum adequacy, teaching approaches, and challenges as predictor variables, in order to determine the proportion of variance in student skill levels attributable to institutional and pedagogical factors. All inferential tests were conducted at the .05 level of significance and were two-tailed. Statistical computations were performed and validated against standard outputs for descriptive and inferential reporting.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles were strictly adhered to throughout the study. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. Respondents' confidentiality and anonymity was ensured, and all data collected was used solely for academic and research purposes.

Data Analysis

2. Section A Demographic Profile of Respondents

Respondent Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Students	200	89.7
GNS Lecturers	15	6.7

Respondent Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Industry Employers	8	3.6
Total	223	100.0

Gender Distribution by Age

Figure 2. Gender distribution across age ranges (N = 223; Male = 117, Female = 106).

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	117	52.5
Female	106	47.5
Total	223	100.0

Research Question 1 What is the level of communication skills among the HND 2 students in the institutions?

Section B assessed students' self-rated communication competence using a 5-point scale (1 = Very Low, 5 = Very High). Analysis was conducted on the 200 student respondents only.

Figure 3. Mean scores for Section B items (student communication skills, $n = 200$). Dashed line = midpoint (3.0).

Research Question 2: Which communication skills do employers consider essential for employability in technical and vocational occupations?

Figure 4. Employer-rated importance of communication skills (Section C, $n = 8$ employers).

The Employability Skills Gap

Figure 5. The employability gap: students' skill levels vs. employers' expectations across matched skill dimensions. Δ values show the gap per skill area.

Employers rated all communication skills as very important ($M = 4.38$), producing a striking gap of 1.80 points against students' self-rated competencies ($M = 2.58$). This gap is consistent across all five skill dimensions and constitutes the central employability deficit of the study.

Research Question 3: To what extent do current technical education curricula incorporate employability-focused communication skills?

Figure 6. Respondent ratings of curriculum adequacy for communication skills (Section D, $n = 223$).

Research Question 4: What teaching and learning approaches are used to develop students' communication skills in technical education programmes?

Figure 7. Frequency of teaching approaches used in communication skills instruction (Section E, n = 223). Green bars exceed midpoint; red bars fall below.

Research Question 5: What challenges hinder the effective development of communication skills among technical education students?

Figure 8. Perceived challenges in communication skills development (Section F, n = 223).

Research Question 6: What strategies can be adopted to bridge the employability gap in communication skills in technical education? Strategy Endorsement (Items F24 & F25)

Strategy	Mean	SD	Level of Endorsement
Increased use of practical and technology-based teaching methods	3.69	1.14	Moderate–Major
Integrating communication skills across all technical courses	3.72	1.18	Moderate–Major

Inferential Statistical Analyses

Figure 9. Section mean scores compared against the scale midpoint (3.0). All results significant at $p < .001$.

Section	Respondents	M	SD	t-value	df	p	Finding
B — Student Skills	Students (200)	2.58	0.45	-13.22	199	< .001	Below midpoint ***
C — Employer Req.	Employers (8)	4.38	0.31	+12.52	7	< .001	Above midpoint ***
D — Curriculum	All (223)	2.44	0.54	-15.44	222	< .001	Below midpoint ***
E — Teaching	All (223)	2.81	0.50	-5.78	222	< .001	Below midpoint ***

Section	Respondents	M	SD	t-value	df	p	Finding
F — Challenges	All (223)	3.72	0.53	+20.58	222	< .001	Above midpoint ***

Note: *** $p < .001$ shows significance. All tests two-tailed.

Pearson Correlation Analysis

Figure 11. Pearson correlation matrix (bubble size = $|r|$; blue = positive; gray = negligible; red = negative).

Variable 1	Variable 2	R	p-value	Interpretation
B — Student Skills	C — Employer Requirements	0.141	.036	Weak positive, significant *
B — Student Skills	D — Curriculum Adequacy	0.075	.266	Very weak, not significant
B — Student Skills	E — Teaching Approaches	0.027	.688	Negligible, not significant
B — Student Skills	F — Challenges	0.061	.365	Negligible, not significant

Variable 1	Variable 2	R	p-value	Interpretation
C — Employer Reqt.	F — Challenges	0.121	.072	Weak, not significant

The only statistically significant correlation was between student communication skills and employer-rated importance ($r = 0.141$, $p = .036$). While positive in direction, the magnitude of the employability gap ($\Delta M = 1.80$) far exceeds what the correlation suggests, underscoring the severity of the deficit.

Multiple Regression Analysis

A multiple regression with student communication skills (Section B composite) as the dependent variable and curriculum adequacy (D), teaching approaches (E), and challenges (F) as predictors yielded $R^2 = 0.031$, meaning only 3.1% of variance in student skill levels was explained by these predictors. This low explanatory power confirms that the skills deficit is systemic, arising from multiple interacting institutional, curricular, and pedagogical failures rather than any single identifiable cause.

Discussion of Findings

This study provides robust empirical evidence that polytechnic students, especially, the graduating students are inadequately prepared for the communication demands of hybrid work environments. Findings are consistent across respondent groups and aligned with the broader literature on employability deficits in TVET institutions. The 1.80-point gap between student competence ($M = 2.58$) and employer expectations ($M = 4.38$) represents a significant employability crisis. These findings align with Andrews and Higson (2008), who reported that employers increasingly prioritize soft skills alongside technical competencies when recruiting graduates but the students tend to lack these skills technical competence alone is insufficient for workplace success. Similarly, Robles (2012) identified communication skills, teamwork, adaptability, and professionalism as essential employability skills required in modern workplaces. The inadequacy of existing curricula ($M = 2.44$) and the over-reliance on lecture-based teaching ($M = 3.72$ for lectures vs. $M = 2.29$ for simulations) offer clear structural explanations. The low R^2 from regression (0.031) confirms the problem is systemic — no single variable explains it. The predominance of teacher-centred instructional approaches and generic language courses limits students' exposure to context-specific and industry-relevant communication practices. In addition, inadequate integration of digital and multimodal communication tools constrains students' readiness for technology-driven and collaborative work environments. These challenges persist despite sustained policy emphasis on employability and workforce readiness. Osuji (2019) suggests that polytechnics in Imo State should integrate communication and professional skills into technical education curricula to improve workplace readiness.

Another major finding of the study revealed weak collaboration between polytechnics and industry in Imo State. This limits students' exposure to workplace realities and reduces opportunities for practical learning. This finding is consistent with Okolie et al. (2020), who reported that inadequate

collaboration between polytechnics and industries contributes to skills mismatch and graduate unemployment. The findings also revealed that inadequate training facilities, outdated equipment, and insufficient digital tools hinder effective skill acquisition. The hybrid work environment requires multimodal tools for the multi tasks expected in the work environment. This finding agrees with Afeti (2018), who noted that inadequate infrastructure in technical institutions affect the quality of training and graduate employability. Evidence from the literature and empirical findings indicates that while technical education institutions are effective in imparting occupational and practical skills, insufficient emphasis is placed on the systematic development of communication competencies essential for workplace effectiveness. Consequently, graduates frequently demonstrate weaknesses in oral communication, technical writing, interpersonal interaction, and digital communication, which negatively affect their employability prospects and career advancement. The findings further reveal a clear mismatch between the communication skills embedded in technical education curricula and those demanded by contemporary workplaces.

Conclusion

Overall, the study concludes that bridging the employability gap in communication skills within technical education requires a deliberate, holistic, and systemic approach that aligns curriculum content, pedagogy, and assessment with labour market expectations. Strengthening communication skills development will not only enhance graduate employability but also contribute to improved productivity and sustainable national development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were proposed:

- Communication skills should be embedded across technical courses rather than restricted to standalone general studies modules.
- Technical education institutions should adopt learner-centred and experiential teaching strategies, including problem-based learning, collaborative projects, role-play, and oral presentations, to enhance practical communication competence as required by departments.
- Educational policymakers and funding agencies should prioritise communication skills development in technical education through targeted funding, curriculum reform initiatives, and quality assurance mechanisms aligned with global employability frameworks.
- Regular professional development programmes should be organised to equip lecturers with skills in employability-oriented pedagogy, digital instruction, and industry-aligned communication practices in order to address the current challenges
- Assessment practices should move beyond traditional written examinations to include continuous and performance-based assessments such as presentations, group projects, technical documentation and reflective portfolio.

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